

Performance Measure of Multipurpose Machine From Single Machine Units

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposed some corollaries to obtain some performance measures of multipurpose machine from its single machine units. It is well known that multipurpose scheduling problems are NP-Hard. Similarly, increases in the number of machine in scheduling problem induce additional computational complexity and new problems, thus the larger the number of machines in a scheduling problem, the higher the degree of computational complexity involved. Therefore, any attempt to obtain the performance objectives of multiple machine environment scheduling problems from its single machine component will make the problems more amenable to solution and increase the efficiency of any proposed algorithm. This paper proposed some rules that can be used to obtain some performance objectives of multipurpose machine environment from its single machine units. It is concluded that partitioning multipurpose machine scheduling problems to its single machine units scheduling will provide a platform for further research work to propose an optimal algorithm for some multipurpose machine scheduling problems.

Keywords: Multi-purpose, complexity, corollaries, efficiency, optimal

INTRODUCTION

The theory of scheduling is characterized by a virtually unlimited number of problem types. (French, 1982, T' Kindt and Billant, 2005).

Based on the number of machine, scheduling problems can be classified into single machine and multi-machine problems (French, 1982, Hoogeveen 2005, Al-harkan, 2008). Single machine scheduling problem is one in which there is only one machine to process all the jobs. Multi-machine or multiprocessor scheduling problem is one in which there are several processors available upon which jobs may be executed. An important class of multiple machine scheduling problem is parallel machine. In parallel machine, In parallel machine environment, there are n jobs J_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$) that have to be processed on m machines M_i , ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$) such that each machines can process at most one job at a time and that each job can be processed on one machine at a time. The existence of parallel machine environment is common in real world flow shop and job shop system (Al-harkan, 2008). Furthermore, there is a special case of parallel machine called the multi-purpose machine (MPM) problem. This is a situation when the processing time of a job depends on the machines, i.e. the job j has processing time of length p_{ij} if it is scheduled on machine M_i . (Zsuzsanna, 2005). In such a case, a job can be processed by any machine of an associated, pre specified subset of the machine set. The multi-purpose machine problem can be described as independent many units of single machine (Vairaktarakis and Cai, 2003).

Since the introduction of scheduling theory in the 1950s, most research like Held and Karp, 1962; Carroll, 1965; Moore, 1968, Lawler, 1973; Smith, 1956; Baker, 1974; Panwalker and Iskander, 1977; Wessenhove and Gelders, 1980; Pinedo, 1995; Phillips et al,

1998, KSA algorithm (2011) etc has been concentrated on single machine scheduling problem. This is probably due to the fact that single machine scheduling problems are less complex compared to their multiple machine counterparts. However, in the real-life problems, multiple machine and in particular multi purpose machine play a role (Hoogeveen, 1990). Most multi purpose machine problems are NP-Hard in nature (Farhad and Vahid 2009) In spite of the abundance of multipurpose machine environments in numerous industries, there has been limited research dealing with this problem. Brucker and Schlie (1990) first introduced the multipurpose parallel machine scheduling problem. Pinedo (1995) showed that multipurpose machines can be considered as a special case of unrelated machines. Brucker and Schlie (1990) derive a polynomial time optimal algorithm for the two-job problem with the objective of makespan minimization. In Brucker and Schlie (1990), Jurish (1995), and Mati and Xie (2004), a subset of machines is associated with each operation of a job in a job shop setting. In all of them, the set of operations for a particular job have to be processed in a particular fixed order.. Jurish (1995) gives a lower bound for the multipurpose machine problem by the generalization of the algorithm given by Brucker and Schlie (1990). Mati and Xie (2004) investigate the complexity of two-job scheduling problems. Brucker et al. (1997) also discuss the complexity status of some multipurpose machine scheduling problems including parallel identical and uniform machine environments. Hurink et al. (1994) develop a tabu-search based algorithm for calculating good heuristic solutions for the MPM job-shop problem. Brucker (2001) discusses additional multipurpose machine problems and their complexity status. Vairaktarakis and Cai (2003) provide a recent example, and the

most extensive effort to address this situation. The focus of their research was on the value of processing flexibility in parallel multipurpose machine environments. They developed and tested several heuristic procedures for solving an array of problems having specific structures, but with randomly generated processing times. They developed an optimal branch and bound procedure to evaluate the performance of the heuristic procedures. In many of the cases that they tested, the optimal algorithm could not solve the problem within the 10 cpu hour limit that they employed.

However, when a large number of jobs have to be processed, several multipurpose machines can be used. In this situation, the assignment of the production batches to single machines has to be determined. This is called partitioning of multipurpose machines. (Crauwels et al., 2006) Thus, determine the performance objective of multipurpose machines from single partition machine unit is the purpose of this paper. To the best of our knowledge, no work has been found in the literature that considers this problem. Therefore, in view of the difficulties and complexity of multipurpose machine scheduling problems and in view of the fact that there optimal or near optimal solution methods for quite a number of single machine scheduling problems, it is desired to explore the possibility of obtain the performance objective of multipurpose machine from its single machine unit, thereby making them amenable to polynomial-time solution methods. Therefore, this work presents some corollaries or principles to obtain the performance measures of multipurpose machine from its partitioned single machine unit. The principles assumed that all the single machine units are run simultaneously and that there is no sequent set up time. Also, these principles are not mathematically proved but logically explained to ascertain their validity.

COMPLEXITIES OF MULTIPLE MACHINE SCHEDULING PROBLEMS

The complexity of an algorithm is a measure of the amount of time and/or space required by the algorithm for an input of a given size (n). (French 1982). The theory of classifying problems based on how difficult they are to solve is called complexity theory. A problem is assigned to the P-problem (polynomial-time) class if the number of steps needed to solve it is bounded by some power of the problem's size. A problem is assigned to the NP-problem (nondeterministic polynomial-time) class if it permits a non deterministic solution and the number of steps to verify the solution is bounded by some power of the problem's size. However, a problem in which it is almost impossible to obtain the optimal solution in feasible time or that it requires 'forbidden' time to obtain optimal solution are called NP-hard problem. In such a problem, it is quite difficult to achieve an optimal solution with traditional optimization approaches owing to the high computational complexity (Farhad and Vahid, 2009; Parviz 2009).

However, scheduling problems are combinatorial in nature (Ajisehiri et al., 2010). In a $n \times m$ problem, where n is the number of jobs and m is the number of machine, the number of possible schedule is given by: $(n!)^m$. In a single machine problem, the number of feasible schedule is given by n!. However, in a multiprocessor problem, the number of machine is always greater than 1. Thus, the number of feasible schedule $= (n!)^m$. This

implies that the higher the number of machine, the number of possible schedule, thus the greater the degree of complexity.

It has been proved that most single machine single criterion scheduling problems has been solved optimally by polynomial time algorithms like EDD rule, SPT rule, MPSW rule, KSA rule, etc. However, most multiple machine scheduling problems (especially with multi criteria) belongs to the NP-Hard class of problems. (Ashwani and Pankaj, 2008).

Performance Measures

Performance measures are criteria by which the performance of any solution method can be measured. It is not easy to state scheduling objectives (French, 1982; Albert and Rabelo, 1998). This is because they are numerous, complex and often conflicting. Scheduling objectives could be completion time based, due date based or inventory based (Kanet and Sridharan, 2000; Dauzere-Perez and Sevaux, 2003).

Literature on the extensive study of scheduling objectives is sparse. Conway et al., (1960) cited four

criteria why Gere (1962) listed about seven scheduling criteria. Perhaps only Beenhakker (1963) has made an attempt by coming out with an extensive list of about 27 distinct scheduling goals (objectives) (Mellor, 1966). However, Conway et al. (1960), Gere (1962), Beenhakker (1963) failed to formulate the mathematical expressions that can be used to compute the considered scheduling objectives. However, Oyetunji (2009) filled this gap to enable researchers working on scheduling problems to know how each of the scheduling objectives can be computed. However, oyetunji (2009) fails to discuss the concept of performance measure equivalence though he discussed both the maximization and minimization objectives. Some of the criteria has described by Oyetunji (2009) are as follows:

- i. The total completion time (C_{tot}) is the sum of all the completion times of the jobs. A common problem is to minimize the total completion time. This leads to what is referred to as MIN-SUM problem. Scheduling criteria based on the total completion time is given by : $(C_{tot}) = \sum_{i=1}^n C_i$
- i. Makespan: The maximum completion time (also called makespan) is the completion time of the last job. A common problem of interest is to minimize C_{max} , or to minimize the completion time of the last job to leave the system . This criterion is usually used to measure the level of utilization of the machine. This leads to MIN-MAX problem. The maximum completion time is given by: $(C_{max}) = \max (C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n)$
- ii. The total flow time (F_{tot}): Flow time is the difference between the completion time and the release date. Total flow time is the sum of the flow times of all the jobs. Scheduling criteria based on the total flow time is given by : $(F_{tot}) = \sum_{i=1}^n F_i = \sum_{i=1}^n (C_i - r_i) = F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + \dots + F_n$

A common problem is to minimize the total flow time. This is because the higher the flow time, the higher the job waiting time before processing and the higher the resources utilized in accomplishing the task.

Total weighted flow time is the sum of all the flow times multiplied by the relative weights of the jobs. A common problem is in minimizing the total weighted flow time. This leads to a MIN-SUM problem. Total weighted flow time $= \sum_{i=1}^n W_i F_i$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^n W_i(C_i - r_i)$$

iii. Total Tardiness: A job is said to be late or tardy if it completes after its due date. Tardiness is similar to lateness except that it carries only positive values. Whenever a job completes before its due dates, its lateness is negative while its tardiness is zero. Scheduling criteria based on tardiness is given by:

$$\text{Total Tardiness (T}_{\text{tot}}) : \sum_{i=1}^n T_i = \sum_{i=1}^n \max \{0, (C_i - d_i)\}$$

A common problem is to minimize the total tardiness.

Total weighted tardiness is the sum of all the tardiness multiplied by the relative weights of the jobs. Total weighted earliness, $(wL_{\text{tot}}) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i T_i = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i [\max \{0, (C_i - d_i)\}]$

A common problem is in minimizing the total weighted tardiness. This leads to a MIN

SUM problem.

iv. Total Earliness: Total earliness (E_j) is also a due date related performance measure but reflects early delivery of jobs and it is defined as summation of earliness of individual jobs.

Total earliness ($E_{\text{tot}}) = \sum_{i=1}^n E_i = \sum_{i=1}^n (d_i - c_i)$ A common scheduling problem is to find a schedule that maximizes the total earliness. Earliness is the opposite of lateness; hence, whenever lateness is negative earliness is positive and whenever lateness is positive earliness is negative.

Total weighted earliness, $(w E_{\text{tot}}) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i E_i = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i (d_i - C_i)$. This is the sum of all the earliness multiplied by the relative weights of the jobs. A common problem is in maximizing the total weighted earliness. This leads to a MAX-SUM problem.

4. Performance Measure Equivalence

Two performance measures are equivalent if a schedule which is optimal with respect to one is also optimal with respect to other and vice versa (French, 1982). French (1982) proved mathematically that for a single machine scheduling problem, the following performance measures are equivalent

- i. The mean completion time, the mean flow time, the mean waiting time, and the mean lateness.
- ii. Similarly, the total completion time, the total flow time, the total waiting time, and the total lateness are also equivalents.

However, the maximum variant of these performance measures; that is C_{max} , F_{max} , W_{max} , and L_{max} are not equivalent though, in a situation of static shop in which the ready date of all job is zero, C_{max} is equivalent to F_{max} . Also, in a situation in which the ready date of all the job is constant, C_{max} and L_{max} are equivalent.

Furthermore, for a bicriteria or multicriteria scheduling problem, the following performance measure are equivalent : Weighted sum of completion time ($\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha C_i(x)$), Weighted sum of flow time ($\sum_{i=1}^n \beta F_i(x)$), Weighted sum of waiting time ($\sum_{i=1}^n \gamma W_i(x)$), and Weighted sum of lateness ($\sum_{i=1}^n \delta L_i(x)$), Weighted sum of earliness ($\sum_{i=1}^n \mu E_i(x)$),

The general procedure to determine whether two or more performance measures are equivalent is to compare their mathematical relationship under the given machine and job environments, if they differ by a constant factor like zero release dates, sum of release date, sum of processing time, constant due date, sum of due dates etc, then the performance measures are said to be equivalent. Applications of performance measure equivalent concept to scheduling problems are

- i. In solving a bicriteria or multicriteria problem, two or more equivalents performance measure are not expected to be presents since a schedule that optimize one will also optimize the other.
- ii. An algorithm proposed for a given objectives can be compared to another existing algorithms that optimizes an equivalent of the objective.
- iii. For a multipurpose machine problem partitioned into its single machine unit, the corollary proposed for a given objective for multipurpose problem from its single machine unit also hold for its equivalent objective

CLASSIFICATION OF PERFORMANCE MEASURES

French (1982) classified scheduling performance measures into three different groups; these are

- i. Criteria Based upon completion time: The main criteria in this category includes; total completion time, total flow time, makespan, maximum flow time, average completion time and average flow time.
- ii. Criteria based upon due dates: The main criteria in this category includes; total lateness, total tardiness, maximum lateness, maximum tardiness
- iii. Criteria based upon the inventory and utilization cost: These include maximum machine idle time, mean number of completed jobs, and mean number of jobs waiting for machine.

THE CORROLARIES

These are set of rules applicable to partitioning scheduling algorithms. When a multipurpose machine scheduling problem is partitioned and converted into a uniprocessor scheduling problem; the performance measures of the multiprocessor problem can be obtained from the uniprocessor problem by the following combination rules. However, various assumptions as in French, (1982) are considered under which the corollaries are valid. Some of the assumptions are

- i. Machines never break down and are available throughout the scheduling period.
- ii. All the machines are available at time zero.
- iii. Processing time, ready time and due date of all the jobs are known, deterministic and finite.
- i. Machines may be idle.
- ii. Splitting of jobs, job cancellation and job pre-emption are not allowed.
- iii. At every moment each processor is assigned to at most one task and each task is processed by at most one processor only.
- iv. All the machines were runs simultaneously (at the same time).
- v. The set-up time is the same for all batches and sequence independent.
- vi. Each machine can process at most one job at a time and that each job can be processed on one machine at a time.
- vii. Each job can be processed to completion by only one machine but machine can process more than one jobs but only one job at a time.

The rules or corollaries are grouped based upon the criteria classification:

Criteria Based upon completion time:

When multipurpose machine problems are partitioned into uniprocessor problems and the processors are runs simultaneously. The performance measures based on completion time of the multipurpose machine can be deduced from its

uniprocessor units as follows:

CORROLARY 1: The makespan of the multiprocessor problems is the highest makespan of any of the uniprocessor units.

Given a set of jobs j_1, j_2, \dots, j_n required to be scheduled and process on a set of machine M_1, M_2, M_3 and M_4 . After applying assignment model, assume;

M_1 assigned to $j_{11}, j_{12}, j_{13}, j_{14}, \dots, j_{1n}$

M_2 assigned to $J_{21}, J_{22}, J_{23}, J_{24}, \dots$

M_3 assigned to $J_{31}, J_{32}, J_{33}, J_{34}, \dots$

M_4 assigned to $J_{41}, J_{42}, J_{43}, J_{44}, \dots$

The scheduling of jobs on each of the assigned machine can be represented by gantt chart as illustrated in figure -----

The makespan of machine 1 is $C1_{max}$ which lies between t_{22} and t_{23} on machine 2

The makespan of machine3 is $C3_{max}$ which lies between t_{23} and t_{24} on machine 2

The makespan of machine4 is $C4_{max}$ which lies between t_{23} and t_{24} on machine 2

Thus, since all the machine were run simultaneously, thus the makespan of M_1, M_3 and M_4 falls within the processing time on M_2 . It follows that the makespan of the multipurpose machine is $C2_{max}$.

CORROLARY 2: The total flow time of the multiprocessor problems is the sum of the total flow time of all the uniprocessor units.

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According to Oyetunji (2009), the flow time of job J_i is the time that job J_i spends in the workshop. The total flow time (F_{tot}) is the sum of all the flow times of all the jobs. Thus in a single machine, each job has an independent flow time and its summation is the total flow time of the machine.

$$\text{Total Flow time } (F_{tot}) = \sum_{j=1}^n F_j$$

Thus for machine 1, Total Flow time

$$(F_{tot}) = \sum_{j=11}^{1n} F_j = F_{11} + F_{12} + F_{13} + \dots + F_{1n}$$

For machine 2, Total Flow time

$$(F_{tot}) = \sum_{j=21}^{2n} F_j = F_{21} + F_{22} + F_{23} + \dots + F_{2n}$$

For machine n, Total Flow time

$$(F_{tot}) = \sum_{j=11}^{nn} F_j = F_{1n} + F_{2n} + F_{3n} + \dots + F_{nn}$$

Thus, regardless of whether the machines were run simultaneously or not, each of the jobs spends a separate time in

the workshop. Furthermore, the multi-purpose machine problem can be described as independent many units of single machine (Vairaktarakis and Cai, 2003). Therefore, if all the jobs in each of the single machine are treated as a single task with the flow time equals to the sum of the flow time of each unit jobs. Thus, it implies that the total flow time of the multipurpose machine is the sum of the flow time of each of the task.

$$\text{Total flow time of multipurpose machine} = (F_{tot})_{mpm} = \sum_{j=11}^{1n} F_j + \sum_{j=11}^{2n} F_j + \dots + \sum_{j=11}^{nn} F_j$$

CORROLARY 3: The total completion time of multipurpose machine problem is the is the sum of the total completion time of all the uniprocessor units.

The total completion time is related to the total flow time by the equation;

$$\sum_{j=1}^n C_j = \sum_{j=1}^n F_j + \sum_{j=1}^n r_j$$

Thus, for multipurpose machine environment,

$$(C_{tot})_{mpm} = (F_{tot})_{mpm} + (\sum_{j=1}^n r_j)_{mpm}$$

Apply the concept of performance measure equivalence, since $(\sum_{j=1}^n r_j)_{mpm}$ is a constant

It follows that the principle that apply to $(F_{tot})_{mpm}$ also valid for $(C_{tot})_{mpm}$

The same rule also applied to total tardiness, total lateness and total earliness which are criteria based upon due dates:

Criteria based upon the inventory and utilization cost:

When multipurpose machine problems are partitioned into uniprocessor problems and the processors are runs simultaneously. The performance measures based upon the inventory and utilization cost:of the multipurpose machine can be deduced from its uniprocessor units as follows:

CORROLARY 4: The maximum machine idle time of multipurpose machine problem is the highest machine idle time of any of the uniprocessor units.

Apply the concept of performance measure equivalence, maximum idle time is related to makespan by the equation;

$$I_M = C_{max} - \sum_{j=1}^n P_j$$

Thus, for multipurpose machine environment, $(I_{max})_{mpm} = (C_{max})_{mpm} - (\sum_{j=1}^n P_j)_{mpm}$

Apply the concept of performance measure equivalence, since $(\sum_{j=1}^n P_j)_{mpm}$ is a constant

It follows that the principle that apply to $(C_{max})_{mpm}$ also valid for $(I_{max})_{mpm}$

CONCLUSION

It is a known fact that the complexities of scheduling problems grows as the number of machine under consideration increases. Also, it is known that optimal or near-optimal solution methods exist for a number of single machine problems. In this paper we have highlighted some useful principle which can be explored to obtained the performance measures of multipurpose machine problem from its single machine units

One of the consequences of this work is that it provides the fulcrum to compare the performance measure of multipurpose machine environment to a single machine environment under the

same condition. The work also provides the basis to justify or criticise the use of multipurpose machine under some given condition. Research work is in progress to justify this thrust.

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